

Proposed Marketing Strategy to Increase Sales for Home Bedding Business (Case Study: Beddo Chingu)

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ABSTRACT: The overall consumption of mattresses in Indonesia has experienced a positive growth rate from 2012. The development of digital businesses in Indonesia has also increased, and it is undeniable that competition in the bedding industry is becoming more intense as more offline bedding sellers shift to online. The increasing competition of the bedding industry can be felt by one of home bedding industry brands, namely Beddo Chingu. Beddo Chingu is a home bedding business that mainly offers bed linen and was established in December 2021. Beddo Chingu uses e-commerce and social media to sell the products. There are promotions that have been applied such as advertising in Shopee, flash sales, discount, post content and paid promotion in Twitter. These promotions didn't last long and Beddo Chingu faced fluctuating sales. This research aims to identify current internal and external conditions of Beddo Chingu, to identify root cause of Beddo Chingu sales issue, and to propose a suitable marketing strategy for Beddo Chingu. This research method uses quantitative and qualitative approaches to create suitable marketing strategies. The analysis tools that will be used in internal analysis are such as STP, Marketing Mix 4P, and VRIO, while for external analysis are PESTEL, Five Forces Model, customer analysis, and competitor analysis. Questionnaires survey with 124 respondents of current customers of Beddo Chingu have been conducted to gain insight from the customer's point of view regarding the marketing mix. In addition, interviews with customers and potential customers were also conducted to obtain more detailed insights from preliminary surveys. From the analysis that has been conducted by researcher, there will be an internal strength and weakness, and external opportunity and threat result that can be called SWOT. Root causes of Beddo Chingu issue are low frequency of promotion, lack of value delivery in content, limited distribution channels, Lack of pattern design variations, limited product Stock Availability due to the long production process, and limited manpower. Based on the TOWS matrix, suitable marketing strategies classified into the marketing mix 4p will be proposed to increase sales of Beddo Chingu.

KEYWORDS: Bed Linen, Marketing strategy, Marketing Mix 4p, SWOT, TOWS Matrix.

INTRODUCTION

MSMEs, or Micro, Small, and Medium-Sized Enterprises, have historically been an important pillar of the Indonesian economy. As stated by Indonesia's Ministry of Cooperatives and Small and Medium Enterprises, there were 64.2 million MSMEs in Indonesia in March 2022, contributing 61.07% to the country's GDP [1]. According to Asosiasi E-commerce Indonesia (IdEA), around 19 million Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) sell on digital platforms under their name. During the corona pandemic, which lasted from May 2020 to February 2022, around 9.9 million MSMEs joined digital platforms [2]. Now that the growth of digital business in Indonesia has increased, it isn't easy to deny that rivalry has intensified as more sellers shift from offline to online platforms to offer their products. Following periods of time and technological advancements, various industries are currently developing extremely rapidly in the commercial world. This success appears in the growing economic environment, which includes the tourism, culinary, and textile industries [3]. The Indonesian mattress market experienced a positive growth rate of 4.8% in 2021 compared to the previous year. Over the span of nine years, overall consumption of mattresses in Indonesia has shown a noticeable increase at an average annual rate of +5.2% [4]. This indicates an increase in demand for mattresses among consumers in Indonesia. This also suggests a steady and consistent growth trend in the market over the given period. The rising consumption and value of the mattress market indicate a positive market prospect for bedding manufacturers, retailers, and related industries in Indonesia. As one of the textile sectors involved in household necessities, the bedding industry will surely set out to provide consumer satisfaction through product qualities that are distinctive from other products. However, given that not all companies can compete and dominate the market in accordance with the goals, this bedding company must face the competition in the face of an increasingly tough rivalry [5]. The increasing competition of the home bedding industry can be felt by one of home bedding industry brands,

namely Beddo Chingu. Beddo Chingu is a small business that is engaged in the home bedding industry. It was founded in December 2021, but started sales in January 2022. Beddo Chingu uses e-commerce and social media to sell the products. In the first month when Beddo Chingu launched the products, the sales were not good. The owner of Beddo Chingu then created a strategy to implement advertisements on Shopee and launched accounts on Twitter and Instagram to make his brand known to the public. This situation didn't last long since Beddo Chingu was unable to compete with the existing competitors, and sales began to decline again. Throughout this research, the author will look at the causes of the issue faced by Beddo Chingu in order to make the business sustain for a long time.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Consumers usually go through a mental process that involves several steps before making a purchase. These steps can be called the buyer's decision process. The buyer decision process consists of five stages, starting with need recognition, information search, evaluation of alternatives, the purchase decision, and postpurchase behavior [6]. The survey and interview for research will focus on gathering information about customer preferences related to the product, price, place, and promotion elements of the marketing mix. A marketing strategy is developed after a thorough examination of the company's internal and external environments. Analyzing the firm's internal conditions requires using segmentation, targeting, and positioning as the core of all marketing strategies [7]. Marketing mix is not a scientific theory but rather a conceptual framework that identifies the key decisions that managers make when customizing their products in order to meet the needs of their customers [8]. The VRIO framework based on the RBV approach is the primary tool for accomplishing internal analysis. Barney identified that a company's internal resources and capability have to demonstrate four VRIO (valuable, rare, inimitable, and organized) attributes in order to be used as a source of business strategy to determine its competitive potential [9]. Analyzing the company's external conditions and understanding the customer's perspective is crucial for developing an effective marketing strategy. The external environment of a company includes all of the factors that can impact its ability to obtain and maintain a competitive advantage. The factors in the firm's general environment into six segments called PESTEL (Political, Economic, Sociocultural, Technological, Ecological, Legal) [10]. Five Forces model that managers need to consider when analyzing the industry environment and formulating competitive strategy refers to Threat of New Entrants, Bargaining Power of Buyers, Bargaining Power of Suppliers, Threat of Substitute Products or Services, Rivalry among Existing Competitors [11]. Understanding customer needs and wants is not always simple. Based on [12] deep insight about customer needs and wants, it is emphasized that understanding and fulfilling these needs and wants is crucial for building meaningful relationships with customers and creating value for them. The competitor analysis needs to be analyzed to be able to predict prospective competitor actions, especially those taken in response to important business actions [13]. Thorough evaluation of internal and external conditions will be conducted to facilitate the SWOT analysis. The advantage of SWOT analysis is that it is beneficial in identifying problems that exist in a company so that it may provide an overview of the organization's state, even if it does not provide a direct solution to the problems faced by the company [14]. Fishbone diagram, also known as the Ishikawa diagram, was designed to identify and analyze the root causes of a problem [15]. The TOWS matrix presents four conceptually different strategies, tactics, and alternatives. In practical terms, certain strategies overlap or can be carried out concurrently and simultaneously. The analysis here is primarily concerned with strategy, but it can also be applied to the formulation required to implement the strategy, as well as more specific activities that support the tactics [16]. Based on the TOWS matrix, suitable marketing strategies classified into the marketing mix 4p will be proposed to increase sales of Beddo Chingu.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research method uses quantitative and qualitative approaches to create suitable marketing strategies. Primary and secondary data will be used for data collection. Interviews and surveys are used to collect primary data, while secondary data is gathered from books, articles, and journals that contain similar theories to Beddo Chingu. Primary data are those that a researcher collects with the intention of addressing a research problem. Primary data consists of qualitative and quantitative data. Interviews and surveys are the primary data collection methods used in this research. For the interview, the researcher will interview consumers and potential customers to gain insight into online buying behavior and perceptions of the Beddo Chingu marketing mix. For the survey, the researcher arranges questionnaires in Google Forms to be filled out by existing customers of Beddo Chingu. The researcher will collect information via a questionnaire regarding Beddo Chingu's product, price, place, promotion, and consumer behavior related

to a bed linen. This survey was conducted to find out the needs of the market and proposed a marketing strategy that will generate new customers. Secondary data for this research that will be used by the author is from online public data and literature. Online public data that is used are available on Shopee, Instagram, Twitter, Google and other social media and platforms. Literature data comes from several sources, such as books, articles, and journals that contain related theories that can be used to support this research. These data are used by the researcher to give insight into the analysis and support the research process.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Customers Analysis

The author conducted comprehensive research to analyze customers by utilizing surveys and interviews with both existing customers and potential customers of Beddo Chingu. This research aimed to gain valuable insights into customer preferences, behaviors, and perceptions regarding Beddo Chingu's marketing mix.

Survey Results

1. Product

The results of the respondents's thoughts on the product are presented in accordance with the seven attributes of the research. The results of the respondents are as follows:

Table I. Product Survey Result

Marketing Mix	Attributes	STS	TS	N	S	SS	Total	Total Score	Average
Product	Beddo Chingu bed linen products use quality types of materials (cold, not faded, durable)	0	12	14	42	56	124	514	4.15
	Beddo Chingu bed linen products are comfortable to use while sleeping	0	4	22	55	43	124	509	4.10
	Beddo Chingu's bed linen products have neat stitching quality	0	5	19	60	40	124	507	4.09
	Beddo Chingu provides friendly and responsive customer service	0	6	25	50	43	124	502	4.05
	I choose a suitable bed linen design according to the room decoration condition	0	10	22	59	33	124	487	3.93
	Beddo Chingu's bed linen products have good enough packaging	0	11	22	59	32	124	484	3.90
	Beddo Chingu products have complete bed linen sizes	0	19	26	46	33	124	465	3.75
	Beddo Chingu's bed linen products have a variety of design patterns	0	41	42	20	21	124	393	3.17

The table above is the result of research on the product marketing mix. Based on the table above, with an average score of 4.15, the majority of respondents agree with the quality of Beddo Chingu product materials, which are cold, do not fade, and are durable. The last statement that states that Beddo Chingu bed linen products provides a variety of design patterns received an average response of 3.17, this indicates that respondents of this survey assume that the variety of design patterns provided by Beddo Chingu is still lacking.

2. Price

The results of the respondents’s thoughts on the price are presented in accordance with the four attributes of the research. The results of the respondents are as follows:

Table II. Price Survey Result

Marketing Mix	Attributes	STS	TS	N	S	SS	Total	Total Score	Average
Price	The price offered by Beddo Chingu products is more affordable than other stores that sell similar products	1	6	12	50	55	124	524	4.23
	The price of Beddo Chingu products is in accordance with my purchasing power	0	6	13	53	52	124	523	4.22
	The price of Beddo Chingu products is in accordance with the quality and benefits that I expect	0	6	13	65	40	124	511	4.12
	The payment method offered by Beddo Chingu is very easy (COD, Shopee pay, Transfer Bank)	1	9	20	57	37	124	492	3.97

According to the table above, the respondents' perceptions of Beddo Chingu products being more affordable than other stores offering similar products received an average score of 4.23, it shows that consumers believe the prices offered by Beddo Chingu are more affordable than those offered by other stores selling similar products. Also the customers find the payment process convenient and accessible. Beddo Chingu offers multiple payment options, including Cash on Delivery (COD), Shopee Pay, and bank transfers, which provide flexibility for customers to choose their preferred method. The average score of 3.97 suggests that customers appreciate the ease and convenience of these payment options.

3. Place

The results of the respondents' thoughts on the place are presented in accordance with the ten attributes of the research. The results of the respondents are as follows:

Table III. TOWS Matrix of Beddo Chingu Table IV.8 Place Survey Result

Marketing Mix	Attributes	STS	TS	N	S	SS	Total	Total Score	Average
Place	I will shop for bed linen at Shopee	1	1	4	54	64	124	551	4.44
	Beddo Chingu online store on shopee is easy to find	0	9	16	56	43	124	505	4.07
	I will shop for bed linen on Tik Tok shop	1	9	18	55	41	124	498	4.02
	I will shop for bed linen on Instagram	3	7	21	51	42	124	494	3.98
	I will shop for bed linen on Tokopedia	2	14	33	59	16	124	445	3.59

I will shop for bed linen at Pasar	2	18	39	44	21	124	436	3.52
I would shop for bed linen on Facebook	2	29	39	34	20	124	413	3.33
I will shop for bed linen at Lazada	4	23	42	43	12	124	408	3.29
I will shop for bed linen on the brand's website	5	27	41	31	20	124	406	3.27
I will shop for bed linen at the mall	4	29	45	32	14	124	395	3.19

Based on the survey responses, it is evident that Shopee is the preferred platform for customers to shop for bed linen. With an average score of 4.44 and a majority of respondents strongly agree that Shopee stands out as the most favored online marketplace among customers. This indicates that Shopee is an effective and suitable distribution channel for Beddo Chingu to sell its products. Tik Tok Shop emerges as the second most popular platform among customers, with an average score of 4.02. Tik Tok's growing popularity and influence in the e-commerce space make it an option for Beddo Chingu to consider as an additional selling platform. By leveraging Tik Tok's user base and interactive features, Beddo Chingu can potentially reach a wider audience and tap into new customer segments. Instagram, with an average score of 3.98, secures the third spot in terms of customer preference for shopping bed linen. Instagram's visual-centric nature and its popularity among younger demographics make it a valuable platform for Beddo Chingu to showcase its products and engage with potential customers. Other platforms such as Tokopedia, Pasar, Facebook, Lazada, Brand Website, and the mall also received relatively positive scores, indicating some level of customer interest and engagement. However, they rank lower in comparison to Shopee, Tik Tok Shop, and Instagram.

4. Promotion

The results of the respondents' thoughts on the promotion are presented in accordance with the twelve attributes of the research. The results of the respondents are as follows:

Table IV. Promotion Survey Result

Marketing Mix	Attributes	STS	TS	N	S	SS	Total	Total Score	Average
Promotion	I know information about similar bed linen products through Shopee Ads	1	1	9	51	62	124	544	4.39
	I know information about similar bed linen products through Influencers	2	3	14	46	59	124	529	4.27
	I know information about similar bed linen products through Tik Tok	3	3	15	50	53	124	519	4.19
	The frequency of consistent promotions on a brand makes me remember the promotion and immediately make a purchase	0	10	19	56	39	124	496	4.00
	Beddo Chingu often provides discounts for certain products	0	10	24	58	32	124	484	3.90

I know information about similar bed linen products through Instagram Ads	0	8	32	48	36	124	484	3.90
I know information about similar bed linen products through Twitter	0	11	27	59	27	124	474	3.82
I know information about similar bed linen products through exhibitions/special events	4	16	21	54	29	124	460	3.71
I know information about similar bed linen products through Facebook Ads	5	20	47	39	13	124	407	3.28
I know information about similar bed linen products through friends/family recommendations	3	27	45	35	14	124	402	3.24
I know information about similar bed linen products through Youtube	4	26	51	26	17	124	398	3.21
Beddo Chingu ads are often found on social media twitter	1	47	41	26	9	124	367	2.96

Based on the survey results, it is clear that Shopee ads are the primary source of information for respondents regarding similar bed linen products. With an average score of 4.39 and a majority of respondents agree that Shopee ads play a significant role in creating awareness and influencing customer perceptions. Influencers also have a significant impact on customers' knowledge of similar bed linen products, with an average score of 4.27. Collaborating with influencers can help Beddo Chingu reach a wider audience and enhance brand visibility. Tik Tok emerges as another valuable channel for information, with an average score of 4.19. As Tik Tok continues to gain popularity, leveraging this platform for promotional activities can help Beddo Chingu capture the attention of potential customers and effectively communicate its product offerings. While Instagram ads, Twitter, events, Facebook ads, word of mouth, and YouTube also play a role in providing information to customers, they received comparatively lower average scores. However, it is still important for Beddo Chingu to maintain a presence on these platforms and explore ways to optimize their promotional strategies.

The majority of respondents agree that Beddo Chingu often provides discounts for certain products with an average score of 3.90, it can be concluded that Beddo Chingu effectively communicates its product promotion discounts to customers. Also based on the respondents' responses, it appears that the perception of Beddo Chingu's ads on Twitter is not favorable. The majority of respondents disagreed with the statement, indicating that they do not often come across Beddo Chingu's ads on this platform. This is further supported by the neutral response from a large number of respondents. The average score of 2.96 indicates that Beddo Chingu's promotions on Twitter do not effectively reach the intended audience. This indicates a lack of consistency and failure to maintain a proper promotion schedule on this platform.

Interview Results

Based on interviews with existing customers of Beddo Chingu, it is evident that the product is highly regarded for its quality, durability, and comfort. However, customers expressed a desire for more variety in pattern designs, particularly floral patterns. The packaging and customer service of Beddo Chingu received positive feedback. Customers primarily purchase bed linens from online platforms such as Shopee and TikTok, and they appreciate affordable pricing and promotional offers. They expressed interest in frequent promotions, giveaways, and live streaming events. The majority of customers were not familiar with Beddo Chingu ads on social media, emphasizing the importance of stronger advertising efforts and engaging content.

Based on interviews with potential customers, a customer's purchase decision-making process starts with realizing the need for bed linen and seeking information through influencers, online marketplaces, and recommendations. Quality, pattern design, price, and

promotions play significant roles in triggering interest. Customers then select their preferred products, brands, and sales promotions before making a final purchase decision. Overall, it is crucial for Beddo Chingu to address customer demands for a wider range of pattern designs, enhance advertising efforts with captivating video content, and leverage influencers to influence purchase decisions. By focusing on these areas, Beddo Chingu can better cater to customer preferences, improve brand visibility, and enhance customer engagement and satisfaction.

SWOT Analysis

After analyzing both the internal and external conditions of Beddo Chingu, a SWOT analysis will be conducted. This analysis is used to evaluate a company's internal strengths and weaknesses, as well as external opportunities and threats. The SWOT analysis of Beddo Chingu is as follows:

Table V. SWOT Analysis of Beddo Chingu

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Good quality material2. Affordable Price3. Guarantee	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Lack of pattern design variation2. Lack of product stock availability3. Limited channel distribution4. Limited manpower5. Low frequency of promotions6. Lack of value delivery in social media content
Opportunities	Threats
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Strong support from the Indonesian government for continuously developing domestic products2. Massive growth of social media and e-commerce user3. The growth of the Textile and Textile Products (TPT) industry4. Government's support to encourage the strengthening of the MSME ecosystem5. Development of 4.0 technological advances in machine	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Low entry barrier2. Products has similarity to many competitor in this market3. Competitor comes with product variety4. High rivalry among competitor in home bedding industry

Root Causes Analysis

The problem faced by Beddo Chingu is fluctuating in sales, which tend to decrease. Fishbone diagrams will be used in this research to identify root causes of fluctuating sales. The diagram of root causes analysis for Beddo Chingu main problem is presented on Figure I:

Figure I. Root Cause Analysis of Beddo Chingu

TOWS Matrix

The TOWS Matrix, also known as the SWOT Matrix, is a strategic tool that helps organizations identify strategic options based on an analysis of internal strengths and weaknesses, and external opportunities and threats. By combining these factors, the TOWS Matrix provides a comprehensive framework for developing strategic insights and making appropriate decisions. In the case of Beddo Chingu, the TOWS Matrix can be used to identify and evaluate strategic options that leverage the company's strengths to capitalize on opportunities, address weaknesses to mitigate threats, and synchronize internal capabilities with external factors. The TOWS Matrix for Beddo Chingu is as follows:

Table VI. TOWS Matrix of Beddo Chingu

	Strengths	Weaknesses
	1. Good quality material 2. Affordable Price 3. Guarantee	1. Lack of pattern design variation 2. Lack of product stock availability 3. Limited channel distribution 4. Limited manpower 5. Low frequency of promotions 6. Lack of value delivery in social media content
Opportunities	S-O Strategies	W-O Strategies
1. Strong support from the Indonesian government for continuously developing domestic products 2. Massive growth of social media and e-commerce user	SO1 Keep in line with market price (S1, S2, O1, O2, O3) SO2 Optimize Advertising (S1, O2, O3)	WO1 Product development in term of pattern design variation (W1, O1, O3, O4, O5) WO2 Looking for alternative vendor (W2, O1, O2, O3, O4, O5) WO3 Expand to Tik Tok (W3, O2, O3, O4)

3. The growth of the Textile and Textile Products (TPT) industry		W04. Hiring Content Creator (S4, S5, S6, O1, O2)
4. Government support to encourage the strengthening of the MSME ecosystem		
5. Development of technological advances in machine		
Threats	S-T Strategies	W-T Strategies
1. Low entry barrier	ST1 Create loyalty program (S1, S2, S3, T1, T4)	WT2 Collaboration with Influencer (W6, T1, T4)
2. Products has similarity to many competitor in this market		WT1 Hold a Giveaway (T1, T2, T3, T4, W5)
3. Competitor comes with product variety		ST2 Conduct Shopee Live Streaming (T1, T4)
4. High rivalry among competitor in home bedding industry		WT3 Create Creative Content (W6, T4)

Based on the TOWS matrix table above, the results show several new marketing strategies that are suitable for use in Beddo Chingu and have been analyzed based on its external and internal conditions.

Proposed New Marketing Strategy

This subchapter will describe how an improved marketing mix strategy was proposed based on the TOWS matrix that comes from internal factors (strengths and weaknesses) and external factors (opportunities and threats) in SWOT. Based on the TOWS matrix, suitable marketing strategies classified into the marketing mix 4p will be proposed to increase sales of Beddo Chingu. The following is Beddo Chingu's proposed new marketing mix strategy.

1. Product

Based on the research findings, the products offered by Beddo Chingu have good quality, comfy, have neat stitching, have long lasting durability, and are at an affordable price. Therefore, Beddo Chingu products are still lacking in terms of design pattern variations and product stock availability. In order to reach the goals, it would be better for Beddo Chingu to develop a product and look for other alternative vendors.

- **Product development in term of pattern design variation**
As mentioned previously, customers said that they were satisfied with the existing quality and price offered by Beddo Chingu but not the variety of pattern design. According to customer interviews, consumers' desire for Beddo Chingu will create additional pattern options. With several color and pattern variations to pick from, it might be easy to make a purchasing decision because average customers and potential target customers choose the bed linens that match the condition of the room decoration. As a result, Beddo Chingu needs to innovate its product pattern in order to differentiate itself from the competition. This must be done in order for Beddo Chingu products to be accepted in the market and increase its competitive position.
- **Looking for Alternative Vendor**
According to the research, customers and potential customers desire a variety of designs. Most of them like pattern designs such as floral, cute character, and abstract design. Beddo Chingu needs to find another vendor who offers designs that are never used by other competitors. So that Beddo Chingu product can differentiate from others and become a pioneer. Other than that, the issue faced by Beddo Chingu was the availability of the product stock itself is sometimes limited due to the long production process, so the production vendor cannot fulfill the request from Beddo Chingu. To control the production

process itself, Beddo Chingu team cannot always control it because the production vendor is located in Bogor and Beddo Chingu's warehouse is located in Cibubur, East Jakarta. Therefore, to increase product stock, it is most effective for Beddo Chingu to look for alternative production vendors that are near the warehouse and can meet the target.

2. Price

Based on the analysis results, it is evident that customers perceive Beddo Chingu's product prices as affordable compared to competitors. This positive perception indicates that Beddo Chingu is successfully aligning its prices with market standards and meeting customer expectations in terms of affordability. The fact that customers are satisfied with the price offered by Beddo Chingu further strengthens the company's ability to keep in line with current prices.

- Keep in line with market price

Customer satisfaction with pricing indicates that Beddo Chingu's pricing strategy is received well with its target market, creating a perceived value that justifies the price of its products. Furthermore, the agreement among customers that the price of Beddo Chingu products is affordable for the expected quality and benefits demonstrates the company's ability to find a balance between pricing and the value proposition it offers. This alignment between price, quality, and perceived benefits is crucial for maintaining a competitive position in the market and ensuring customer satisfaction. Beddo Chingu can maintain current market rates by continually meeting customers expectations and offering affordable prices that are seen as reasonable for the quality given. The positive feedback from customers not only demonstrates the efficiency of Beddo Chingu's pricing approach but also provides an opportunity for the company to expand its market position and attract new customers who value affordability without sacrificing product quality.

3. Place

Based on customer interviews and surveys, Shopee is the most popular channel for purchasing bed linens. Followed by Tik Tok, Instagram, Tokopedia, Pasar, Facebook, Lazada, Brand Website, and Mall. According to research by Katadata, the most visited e-commerce site in Indonesia in 2022 was Shopee, with 191 million visitors, followed by Tokopedia, Lazada, Bilibili, and Bukalapak. Beddo Chingu's main channel for promotion is currently Shopee, indicating that the platform used is already in accordance with the results of this research. As a result, Shopee would be an appropriate channel for selling the products. Other than Shopee, Beddo Chingu products can be found on other distribution channels like Instagram and Twitter. According to the survey, TikTok is the second preferred channel for purchasing bed linen, but Beddo Chingu is not currently active on TikTok. Beddo Chingu may be able to take advantage of this opportunity to increase awareness among potential customers.

- Sign up a store on Tik Tok

TikTok Shop is considered to be gaining traction in Indonesia's digital ecosystem. The ease of shopping with a short video social media service allows this TikTok function to provide not only a desired product but also an enjoyable shopping experience. The convenience of shopping via a short video social media service makes this TikTok feature a threat to major e-commerce businesses. Therefore, Beddo Chingu can take advantage of this trending application to register a store on Tik Tok in order to reach more customers.

4. Promotion

According to the findings of this research, Beddo Chingu's promotions are quite rare in comparison to competitors, resulting in a lack of brand recognition. In addition, some respondents thought that Beddo Chingu's content was not effective at communicating the value of its products. Based on responses from potential consumers who were interviewed, respondents said Beddo Chingu has to communicate and show the value of its products more so that people will understand the advantages of products. According to surveys and interviews, the majority of respondents learned about the similar product and brand from Shopee ads, followed by Influencers, Tik Tok, Instagram ads, and others. Therefore, Beddo Chingu needs to carry out a new improvement marketing strategy so that it can increase brand awareness and achieve good sales. Following is the proposed marketing strategy for Beddo Chingu that will be used in the future.

- Optimize Advertising in Shopee

Based on the research findings, it is evident that Shopee is the primary channel through which the majority of respondents obtain information about bed linen or brands. This emphasizes the significance of having a presence on Shopee, as it is a suitable platform for selling Beddo Chingu products. Beddo Chingu should focus on optimizing its advertising efforts in

order to maximize the potential of Shopee as a sales channel. It is mentioned that previous Shopee advertising was carried out with auto-select search keywords determined by Shopee, and Beddo Chingu was not aware of the specific search keywords suggested by the platform. As a result, there is a need for optimization in the advertising process. Using keywords that consumers regularly use while searching for bed linen is one approach to optimizing Shopee advertising. Keywords such as "Sprei," "Sprei aesthetic," and "Sprei floral" can be used in Beddo Chingu's Shopee advertising, for example. Beddo Chingu can raise the visibility of its products and improve its chances of reaching its target audience by aligning the keywords in the ads with common consumer search phrases.

Additionally, it is important to ensure that the store and product information on the store description and product description pages contain relevant keywords. Beddo Chingu can improve the search engine optimization (SEO) of its Shopee ads by using keywords that appropriately describe the store and product offerings. This optimization may increase the visibility of Beddo Chingu products in search results, increasing the chances of acquiring new customers.

Overall, Beddo Chingu may improve its exposure and the effectiveness of its advertising efforts on Shopee by optimizing the usage of keywords in Shopee advertising and aligning them with customer search behavior. This strategic strategy can assist Beddo Chingu in maximizing its Shopee existence, reaching a larger customer base, and eventually generating sales and growth.

- **Create Creative Content**

Based on the survey and interview, potential customers find that the content of Beddo Chingu does not effectively communicate the benefits and additional value of products. In order to effectively communicate the value and competitive advantages of Beddo Chingu, Beddo Chingu must be able to create content that can engage customers' feelings about owning the product. Beddo Chingu can use interesting photos or short videos to tell stories related to bed linen or sleep, one of which is to create a story about the changes in sleep atmosphere and visualize the product's advantages. With such a content, users feel invited to follow a visual journey by feeling every part of the story.

- **Hiring Content Creator**

Beddo Chingu has difficulties developing appealing content owing to poor management capabilities in content development knowledge, so the content shown does not attract many customers. Meanwhile most potential customers prefer to find information about bed linen through social media content. As a result, in order to meet potential customers' wants, it is indeed essential to hire a dedicated content creator to handle the company's content activities. This content creator will play a crucial role in addressing the existing content development knowledge gap and meeting the wants of potential customers.

- **Collaboration with Influencer**

Based on the results of the interview and survey, it can be seen that respondents get information about bed linen brands, one of which comes from Influencers. By using Influencers, potential customers can find Beddo Chingu products and buy them. Currently, Beddo Chingu does not collaborate with any influencers, unlike competitors who even have brand ambassadors. In addition, they can promote Beddo Chingu's bed linens among their fans. Working with Influencers can be an opportunity to widen reach and increase customer trust in the brand. In addition, they can help introduce Beddo Chingu's bedding products and recommend them to their followers. Therefore, Beddo Chingu needs to collaborate with influencers to increase traction.

- **Conduct Live Streaming**

Live streaming on Shopee and Tik Tok can be utilized to promote sales. Beddo Chingu can use the live streaming feature to do product reviews, directly answer consumer inquiries, and provide additional product information. This can help increase customer trust and engagement with the brand. Furthermore, Beddo Chingu could offer special offers such as discounts or giveaways via live streaming. Live streaming is supposed to raise customers' awareness of the product and encourage them to buy it.

- **Hold a Giveaway**

Based on the research findings, most customers want more promotion from Beddo Chingu. Beddo Chingu will hold giveaways where customers have a chance to win free bed linen or other related products. This will be done through Shopee or Tik Tok Live. It will encourage customers to participate by following, tap like, and share the current Live. This will increase brand awareness and interact with customers to try the products offered by Beddo Chingu.

- **Create Loyalty Program**

To keep repeat customers, Beddo Chingu will apply a loyalty program specifically for the purchase of bed linen. Beddo Chingu will offer incentives such as discounts, exclusive offers, or free products to customers who purchase products often. A points-based system will be applied to this program where customers can accumulate points with each purchase and redeem them for rewards. This is expected to encourage repeat purchases and build customer loyalty.

CONCLUSION

In the research conducted, the author has gained insights into both the internal and external conditions of Beddo Chingu current state. At present, Beddo Chingu's competitive position is relatively weak compared to its competitors. The brand suffers from low awareness among consumers. Beddo Chingu still lacks in promotion compared to other competitors. Furthermore, Beddo Chingu encounters a disadvantage in terms of pattern designs offered, as they are relatively limited compared to its competitors who provide a wide array of design options. However, on the positive side, Beddo Chingu leads in offering affordable prices compared to its competitors. Beddo Chingu's external conditions are characterized by intense competition resulting from low entry barriers in the bedding industry. Beddo Chingu faces the challenge of differentiating itself from competitors to attract consumers. As a new player, Beddo Chingu was positioned at a high level of competition in the industry and needed to work hard to carve out a significant role. The researcher identified various root causes that caused Beddo Chingu's fluctuating sales. The first is that Beddo Chingu products lack variation in design patterns and have limited product availability due to the lengthy manufacturing procedure. Following that, Chingu products are mainly available on Shopee, Twitter, and Instagram, while the majority of current and potential customers prefer to shop for bed linen on Shopee and Tik Tok. The biggest issue that Beddo Chingu is facing is a lack of promotion, which has resulted in low brand awareness. Beddo Chingu lack of promotion, specifically in handling of Shopee ads, content, and sales promotion. In addition, due to Beddo Chingu's management's limitations in terms of creating creative content. The content provided by Beddo Chingu fails to properly convey the advantages of the product. Based on the TOWS Matrix analysis conducted for Beddo Chingu, several new marketing mix strategies can be identified to align with the company's internal strengths and weaknesses, and external opportunities and threats. These strategies aim to optimize Beddo Chingu's marketing efforts, increase competitive advantage, and capitalize on market opportunities. The proposed new marketing mix strategies for Beddo Chingu to increase sales are product development in term of pattern design variation, looking for alternative vendor, keep in line with market price, sign up a store on Tik Tok, optimize advertising in Shopee, create creative content, collaboration with Influencer, conduct live streaming, hold a giveaway, and create loyalty program.

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